

Studies on cavity shaped polycyclic thiaarenes : Short and efficient synthesis of 2,12-dimethylantra[1,2-*b*][8,7-*b*]bisthiophene and anthra[1,2-*b*]thiophene[†]

Gandhi K. Kar, Manas K. Haldar, Susmita Gupta, Dipanjan Pan and Jayanta K. Ray*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur-721 302, India

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A short, efficient and high yielding synthesis of anthra[1,2-*b*][8,7-*b*]bisthiophene (5) and anthra[1,2-*b*]thiophene (12) is described. Compound 5 has been synthesised by condensation of methyl thioglycolate with the bis-chloroaldehyde 1 to give the 2,10-dicarbomethoxyanthra[1,2-*b*][8,7-*b*]bisthiophene (2). Subsequent hydrolysis of the diester followed by decarboxylation of the resulting diacid 3 produces 4,5,7,8-tetrahydroanthra[1,2-*b*][8,7-*b*]bisthiophene (4) which is aromatized with DDQ to furnish compound 5. Following the similar sequence of reaction on the chloroaldehyde 8 anthra[1,2-*b*]thiophene (12) has been synthesised. Compound 5 on further methylation with *n*-BuLi and MeI results in the formation of the dimethyl derivative 6.

Greater similarities in physical and chemical properties between thiophene and benzene and between their corresponding derivatives have been the subject of much speculation till the concept of bioisoterism was developed¹⁻³. The two groups -CH=CH- and -S- have been called ring equivalents and presently are considered as bioisosters by medicinal chemists².

The environmental occurrence of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) and their aza analogue polycyclic azaarenes (PAA) has been widely studied in last few decades because of the adverse properties like mutagenic and/or carcinogenic activities⁴ displayed by such compounds.

A large number of compounds as well as their oxidative metabolites (*trans*-dihydrodiol derivatives) have been reported as a consequence of extensive research by various groups⁵⁻⁷. However, analogous sulfur heterocycles (in which one benzene ring of PAH has been replaced by thiophene ring) which also have been found to occur concomitantly with PAH in numerous mixtures like coal derived products and shale oils⁸⁻¹⁴ etc. were not investigated in details towards their mutagenic and/or carcinogenic properties. Although some data suggest that some of the polyaromatic sulfur compounds are mutagenic and or carcinogenic¹⁵⁻¹⁸. We still know very little of the adverse biological properties of these heterocyclic compounds as compared to those of related PAH's. This is mainly due to lack of standard materials in sufficient amount and in pure forms.

Since last few decades there have been a tremendous development in the synthesis of polycyclic aromatic sulfur heterocycles all around the world¹⁹ and particularly in US by Castle and Lee's group²⁰.

For quite some times in our laboratory, we have directed

our efforts towards the synthesis of polycyclic thiophene derivatives and their oxidative metabolites. As a result of this we have already reported the synthesis of some novel thiaarene derivatives^{21,22}. Very recently, we have communicated the first total synthesis of *trans*-dihydrodiol derivative of acenaphtho[1,2-*b*]benzo[*d*]thiophene, as an oxidative metabolite of the corresponding thiaarene²³.

Here we report the synthesis of anthra[1,2-*b*][8,7-*b*]bisthiophene (5) (a novel cavity shaped bis-thiophene analogue of mutagenic dibenz[*a,i*]anthracene) and anthra[1,2-*b*]thiophene (12) (a thiophene analogue of benz[*a*]anthracene) both with bay region in its moiety and having 'S' atom in this region. The key step of the synthesis involved the construction of the thiophene moiety by condensation of thioglycolic ester with suitable β -chloro- α,β -unsaturated chloroaldehydes.

The synthesis of compound 5 was achieved, in overall high yield, in only four steps starting from 1,8-dichloro-3,4,5,6-tetrahydroanthracene-2,7-dialdehyde²⁴ (1) (Scheme 1). Thus the chloroaldehyde 1 was condensed with methylthioglycolate/Et₃N in pyridine at 45-50° followed by ring closure with 50% aq. KOH to obtain 2,10-dicarbomethoxy-4,5,7,8-tetrahydroanthra[1,2-*b*][8,7-*b*]bisthiophene (2) as a yellowish white solid in 75% yield. Alkaline hydrolysis (KOH, EtOH-H₂O, reflux) of the diester 2 afforded the diacid 3 in excellent yield and this on decarboxylation with copper-chromite catalyst in boiling quinoline resulted in the formation of 4,5,7,8-tetrahydroanthra[1,2-*b*][8,7-*b*]bisthiophene (4) as a colourless solid in 95% yield. Finally, aromatisation of the resulting tetrahydroderivative 4 with DDQ in refluxing benzene furnished the target compound 5 as a pale yellow solid, in excellent yield. It has

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been found that presence of methyl groups in the bay region of PAH increases the mutagenic activity through the formation of benzyl carbocation. In order to study the effect of methyl group in this bithiophene **5**, we have synthesised 2,10-dimethylantracene[1,2-*b*][8,7-*b*]bithiophene (**6**). Thus compound **5** was treated with *n*-BuLi/TMEDA in THF at -60° and then quenched with MeI to produce the dimethyl derivative **6** in very good yield. The compounds **5** and **6** contain two bay regions in their molecular frameworks and having 'S' atoms in these regions, while compound **6** in addition contain two methyl groups near bay region. The study of mutagenicity of these compounds may throw some new light upon the relationship of the polyaromatic hydrocarbons and its thiophene analogue.

Scheme 1. Reagents and condition : (i) Methyl thioglycolate, Et_3N , pyridine, RT, 1 h, then at $45-50^\circ$, 30 min, then 50% KOH, $15-20^\circ$, 30 min, (ii) KOH, $\text{EtOH-H}_2\text{O}$, reflux, 3 h, (iii) Cu-chromite, quinoline, reflux, 4 h, (iv) DDQ, benzene, 8 h, (v) *n*-BuLi (3-4 equiv.), TMEDA, THF, -60° , 30 min under argon, then MeI (excess), 20 min at -60° , then 1 h at RT.

Our second target molecule anthra[1,2-*b*]thiophene (**12**) is a thiophene analogue of benz[*a*]anthracene, a well-known carcinogenic polyaromatic hydrocarbon, present in the biosphere as environmental pollutants. Though anthra[1,2-*b*]thiophene was known for a long time but only two syntheses of this compound have been reported so far^{20a,25}, but both the syntheses suffers from low yield and complexity in work-up procedures. We have developed, a new, short and efficient route for the synthesis of anthra[1,2-*b*]thiophene, starting from the ketone **7** as per Scheme 2.

The ketone **7**²⁶ was converted to the chloroaldehyde **8** in excellent yield by treatment with Vilsmeier-Haack reagent (POCl_3/DMF). Condensation of the chloroaldehyde **8** with methyl thioglycolate in presence of triethylamine in pyri-

dine followed by treatment with 50% aqueous KOH as described for the synthesis of **2**, afforded the thiophene ester derivative **9** in a single-pot reaction. Hydrolysis of **9** ($\text{KOH}/\text{EtOH-H}_2\text{O}$) followed by decarboxylation of the resulting acid **10** with copper-chromite in boiling quinoline afforded 4,5,7,8,9,10-hexahydroanthra[1,2-*b*]thiophene (**11**) as a

Scheme 2. Reagents and condition : (i) POCl_3 , DMF, $60-65^\circ$, 6 h, (ii) methyl thioglycolate, Et_3N , pyridine, $45-50^\circ$, 2 h, then 50% KOH (aq.), $15-20^\circ$, 30 min, (iii) KOH, $\text{EtOH-H}_2\text{O}$, reflux, 3 h, (iv) Cu-chromite, quinoline, reflux, 6.5 h, (v) DDQ, benzene, reflux, 16 h.

colourless oil in 93% yield. Aromatization of **11** with DDQ in refluxing benzene produced anthra[1,2-*b*]thiophene (**12**) 4,5,7,8,9,10-hexahydroanthra[1,2-*b*]thiophene (**11**) as a colourless oil in 93% yield. Aromatization of **11** with DDQ in refluxing benzene produced anthra[1,2-*b*]thiophene (**12**) in 89% yield as a shining colourless solid.

The striking features of these syntheses are the ready availability of the starting materials, extremely good yield in most of the steps, and easy reaction conditions. Thus this method is undoubtedly superior to the previously reported methods.

The mutagenic study of these compounds will be taken up shortly and will be reported elsewhere.

Experimental

All the m.p.s. are uncorrected and was determined with one side open glass capillary using sulfuric acid bath. The solvents used were purified and dried as per standard procedure. ^1H NMR (200 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (50 MHz) spectra were recorded on a Bruker FACF-200 FT NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 800 machine. Elemental analysis data were obtained from C.D.R.I., Lucknow (India).

2,10-Dicarbomethoxy-4,5,7,8-tetrahydroanthra[1,2-b][8,7-b]bisthiophene (2) : To a stirred solution of the bis-chloroformyl derivative (**1**; 615 mg, 2 mmol) and methyl thioglycolate (510 mg, 4.8 mmol) in pyridine (10 ml) at 0–5°, triethylamine (0.8 ml) in pyridine (10 ml) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h and at 45–50° for 30 min. It was then cooled to 15–20°, an aqueous 50% KOH solution (1 ml) added and stirred vigorously for 0.5 h. The mixture was poured into ice-water with stirring and then extracted with chloroform. The organic layer was washed successively with water, ice-cold 5% HCl solution and with water and then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent followed by purification [column chromatography : silica gel/4 : 1 benzene-pet. ether (b.p. 60–80°)], afforded the title compound as a yellowish white solid (75%, 610 mg), m.p. 244–245° (benzene) (Found : C, 64.17; H, 4.14. $C_{22}H_{18}O_4S_2$ calcd. for : C, 64.39; H, 4.39%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1708 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 2.78 (4H, t), 2.83 (4H, t), 3.89 (6H, s), 7.08 (1H, s), 7.41 (1H, s), 7.58 (2H, s); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 23.7, 28.8, 52.07, 118.359, 128.22, 129.6, 130.0, 133.7, 135.6, 137.6, 142.5, 162.7.

4,5,7,8-Tetrahydroanthra[1,2-b][8,7-b]bisthiophene-2,10-dicarboxylic acid (3) : To compound **2** (200 mg, 0.49 mmol) dissolved in THF (15 ml) a solution of KOH (200 mg) in water (5 ml) and ethanol (15 ml) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 3 h. Solvent was then removed as much as possible by distillation and the residue was diluted with water, cooled and acidified with conc. HCl. The precipitated acid was filtered, dissolved in sodium carbonate solution, treated with little activated charcoal and filtered. The filtrate on acidification with conc. HCl afforded **3** as light yellow solid (160 mg, 86%), m.p. >270° (Found : C, 62.51; H, 3.42. $C_{20}H_{14}O_4S_2$ calcd. for : C, 62.82; H, 3.66%); ν_{max} 1679 cm^{-1} .

4,5,7,8-Tetrahydroanthra[1,2-b][8,7-b]bisthiophene (4) : The thiophene derivative (**3**; 150 mg, 0.39 mmol) taken with quinoline (3 ml) and catalytic amount of copper-chromite catalyst (30–40 mg) was refluxed for 4 h. The mixture was then diluted with dichloromethane and filtered to separate the catalyst. The filtrate was poured into ice-cold concentrated HCl (10 ml), diluted with water, and extracted with dichloromethane. The organic layer was successively washed with dil. HCl, 5% sodium bicarbonate solution and water. The organic layer on drying (sodium sulphate) and removal of solvent led to a solid which was purified by column chromatography [silica gel/pet. ether (b.p. 60–80°)]. Compound **4** was obtained as a colourless solid (110 mg, 95%), m.p. 127–128° (Found : C, 73.15; H, 4.33.

$C_{18}H_{14}S_2$ calcd. for : C, 73.46; H, 4.76%); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 2.79–2.98 (8H, m), 6.91 (2H, d, $J \sim 5.0$ Hz), 7.07 (1H, s), 7.16 (2H, d, $J \sim 5.0$ Hz), 7.35 (1H, s).

Anthra[1,2-b][8,7-b]bisthiophene (5) : A mixture of **4** (93 mg, 0.31 mmol) and DDQ (217 mg, 0.95 mmol) in dry benzene (15 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. After usual work up and purification [column chromatography : silica gel/pet. ether (b.p. 60–80°)] **5** was obtained as pale yellow solid (75 mg, 82%), m.p. 227–228° (Found : C, 74.26; H, 3.32. $C_{18}H_{10}S_2$ calcd. for : C, 74.48; H, 3.44%); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 7.50 (2H, d, $J \sim 5.1$ Hz), 7.58 (2H, d, $J \sim 5.1$ Hz), 7.80 (2H, d, $J \sim 8.8$ Hz), 7.87 (2H, d, $J \sim 8.8$ Hz), 8.52 (1H, s), 8.88 (1H, s).

2,10-Dimethylantra[1,2-b][8,7-b]bisthiophene (6) : To a stirred solution of compound **5** (20 mg, 0.068 mmol) and TMEDA (0.3 ml) in THF (6 ml) at –60° under argon atmosphere, *n*-BuLi (0.4 ml of 1.6 *M* solution) was added dropwise. The resulting dark brown solution was stirred at –60° for 30 min, then MeI (excess, ~0.1 ml) added, stirring continued for 15 min at –60° and then at RT for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then decomposed with ice-water and extracted with $CHCl_3$. The organic layer was washed thoroughly with 5% ice-cold HCl and water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed. The crude product thus obtained was purified by column chromatography [neutral alumina/pet. ether (b.p. 60–80°)] followed by recrystallization with pet. ether (b.p. 60–80°)-chloroform mixture to furnish **6** as light yellow solid (16 mg, 72%), m.p. 218–219°; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 2.71 (6H, s), 7.13 (2H, s), 7.67 (2H, d, $J \sim 8.8$ Hz), 7.80 (2H, d, $J \sim 8.8$ Hz), 8.46 (1H, s), 8.65 (1H, s).

1-Chloro-3,4,5,6,7,8-hexahydroanthracene-2-aldehyde (8) : To ice-cold DMF (7.0 ml), $POCl_3$ (4.6 g, 30 mmol) was added dropwise. The mixture was stirred at 0–5° for 10 min. To it a solution of 1-oxo-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydroanthracene **7** (4.0 g, 20 mmol) in DMF (25 ml) was added dropwise maintaining the temperature at 0–5°. The mixture was allowed to attain room temperature gradually and then heated at 60–65° for 6 h. With progress of time, the colour of reaction mixture became dark brown. It was then cooled to room temperature, decomposed with ice-cold solution of saturated sodium acetate (excess) and extracted with ether. The organic layer was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed to furnish **8** as a pale yellow liquid. It was purified by passing through neutral alumina and eluting with pet. ether (b.p. 60–80°), (4.3 g, 87.2%); ν_{max} (neat) 1667 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 1.65–1.95 (4H, m), 2.45–2.95 (8H, m), 6.95 (1H, s), 7.6 (1H, s), 10.5 (1H, s).

2-Carbomethoxy-4,5,7,8,9,10-hexahydroanthra[1,2-b]thiophene (9) : To a stirred solution of the chloroformyl

derivative (**8**; 986 mg, 4 mmol) and methyl thioglycolate (700 mg, 6.5 mmol) in pyridine (5 ml) at 0–5°, Et₃N (0.8 ml) in pyridine (5 ml) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was gradually allowed to attain RT, stirred at 40–50° for 2 h and then cooled to 15–20°. An aqueous 50% KOH solution (1 ml) was added to it and stirred vigorously for 0.5 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice-water with stirring and then extracted with chloroform. The organic layer was washed with water, 5% HCl solution and again with water and then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent followed by purification [column chromatography : silica gel/pet. ether (b.p. 60–80°)] afforded **9** (640 mg, 54%), m.p. 117–118° (ethanol) (Found : C, 72.12; H, 5.74. C₁₈H₁₈O₂S calcd. for : C, 72.48; H, 6.04%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1693 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 1.61–1.9 (4H, m), 2.5–2.86 (8H, m), 3.83 (3H, s), 6.86 (1H, s), 7.07 (1H, s), 7.53 (1H, s).

4,5,7,8,9,10-Hexahydroanthra[1,2-b]thiophene-2-carboxylic acid (10) : To a solution of **9** (900 mg, 3.02 mmol) in ethanol (40 ml), 5% aqueous KOH solution (15 ml) was added and refluxed for 3 h. Ethanol was then distilled off and the residue diluted with water, extracted with ethyl acetate to remove neutral matter (if any), treated with active charcoal and filtered hot. Acidification of the filtrate with conc. HCl afforded the desired solid. It was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethyl acetate to produce **10** as a colourless solid (720 mg, 84%), m.p. 235–236°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1662 cm⁻¹.

4,5,7,8,9,10-Hexahydroanthra[1,2-b]thiophene (11) : The acid (**10**; 700 mg, 2.46 mmol) was refluxed with quinoline (10 ml) in the presence of copper-chromite (80–100 mg) for 6.5 h, then diluted with ether and filtered to separate the catalyst. The filtrate was poured in ice-cold conc. HCl (15 ml), diluted with water and extracted with ether. The organic layer was successively washed with dil. HCl, 5% sodium bicarbonate solution, water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent afforded a light brown oil which on purification by column chromatography [silica gel/pet. ether (60–80°)] furnished **11** as a colourless oil (558 mg, 93%); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 1.79–1.87 (4H, m), 2.77–2.95 (8H, m), 6.90 (1H, s), 6.93 (1H, d, *J* ~4.5 Hz), 7.12 (1H, s), 7.13 (1H, d, *J* ~4.5 Hz).

Anthra[1,2-b]thiophene (12) : Compound **11** (155 mg, 0.65 mmol) was refluxed with DDQ (485 mg, 2.14 mmol) in dry benzene (15 ml) for 16 h. After cooling to room temperature, it was filtered through a neutral alumina column and eluted with pet. ether (b.p. 60–80°). Removal of the solvent afforded a shining white solid (135 mg, 89%), m.p. 119–120° (lit.^{20a} 120°).

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